

RESPONSE PAPER

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Citation and Quotations (EUCLID 2019, 6-9)
4. Writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)
7. Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-59)

THE IMPORTANCE OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Depending on context and milieu, academic writing sometimes has a bad reputation. It invokes thoughts of lengthy and complicated sentences that are enriched with an abundance of foreign and technical terms that decrease comprehensibility. The coursework of the first period manages to dispel these notions by doing two main things. Firstly, it emphasizes the importance of clear, simple, and precise language. This is important in order not to confuse or even mislead readers and to make it accessible to a broad audience. Overusing Latin expressions or abbreviations or acronyms is one of several elements that writers should avoid. Secondly, the coursework outlines the reasons for and benefits of adopting an academic style, which is achieved both by the overall structure of the text as well as through aspects like proper citation, lists of references, and providing more than one viewpoint. If adhered to properly, rules and best practices of academic writing ensure that science and its findings are enriching both academia and society.

2) STRUCTURE AND CONSISTENCY

One of the most important lessons I have taken away from this coursework is to invest a lot of care into the consistency and structure of my work. To ensure that writing can be understood, there is a standardized format that academic **essay writing** follows: an introductory chapter that fulfills the role of an abstract, the main body of the thesis, and the conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3). Because of the dual function of the introduction, it is best to write it after completing the rest of the thesis to know its full scope and content.

Within the main chapters of a thesis, headings are one of the most important elements to provide structure (EUCLID 2019, 13). They divide the main arguments into logical sections and allow for easy skimming, getting an overview of the thesis as well as returning to previous chapters if you require a second reading. In my opinion, well-chosen headings already tell the readers more about the thought process and the construction of arguments so that reading the table of contents itself provides an overview of the thesis.

During the writing process, it might become clear that some information is best supported by tables. When creating a table, all elements of the table have to be properly named and all data needs to be easily assignable to the respective categories. Following Turabian, tables should not extend over more than one page if they are part of the main body (Turabian 2018, 371). If they are longer or are not of the highest importance for the topic at hand, tables should be moved to the appendix. This marks an interesting change for me since I learned to include all tables in the appendix to avoid inflating text lengths and for collecting all tables in one place. However, the process outlined in the study materials makes tables more easily accessible and lets readers see the data the moment they come in touch with a concept. If the research topic happens to be more data-driven, I remain a bit worried whether this might overload the work and decrease readability, thus working against the other points outlined in this section.

As a writer, I should keep my work structured and consistent. Following a proper template and rules for using indentation, italics, and other linguistic and stylistic markers avoid confusing your readers. The video that was part of the study material for this period proves to be extremely helpful for navigating all the settings of the software and applying the necessary templates. Another way to reduce confusion and provide clarity is to not let your readers guess what hypothesis you are researching or what arguments you want to make with your work. State the main thesis of your work early (EUCLID 2019, 1), and then make sure that all following arguments play a part in discussing this thesis.

3) LINGUISTIC CLARITY

It is not enough to keep the structure of your work clear. The same if not closer attention has to be paid to keeping your language precise and understandable. Conveying and summarizing an idea succinctly is often harder than writing long-winded texts. To me, this is the best indicator to see if a person understands their research topic. If you write in

simple and precise language, you cannot hide bad ideas or fraudulent research behind elaborate, complicated prose. This can be achieved by a mixture of different elements.

Quality can be found in simplicity. That is why I try to adhere to the rule of not writing sentences that extend over more than five lines that the course material also outlines. Both in my academic and my professional career, I have corrected and proofread texts and too often, the beginning statement of a sentence would be forgotten by the time of the fifth comma. This serves neither the author nor the reader. The same is true for paragraphs. I found the idea very insightful that each paragraph should be about one main argument or point and therefore, should not be longer than twenty lines. This not only forces writers to be more precise but also encourages thinking more closely about the succession of arguments. I will start paying more attention to the ideas included in each paragraph and divide arguments into sub-arguments should this be necessary.

As opposed to this, I will need to get used to the first person singular when writing academic texts. During my studies at German universities, it was one of the recurring lessons instilled in me to never use the first person singular. So I was surprised to see the opposite being true for response papers and it makes me curious to know whether this is a language-specific difference or whether there has been a shift happening since I finished my last degree several years ago.

The course material also provided a variety of helpful language hints and summaries that I am sure I will refer to several times throughout my study. Most importantly, it laid out the numerous fine **differences between GB and US English**, from terminology over slang to spelling, and underlined the importance of sticking to either GB or US English. Furthermore, the **CMS Crib Sheet** provided rules for when to capitalize words, when to use italics, or the differences between quotation marks. “Never confuse your reader” was my main takeaway from this whole segment (EUCLID 2019, 51). The chapter that perhaps showcases this best is the one about **Latin abbreviations and expressions**. Instead of filling your essay with numerous academic-sounding Latin proverbs, we are encouraged to avoid them as much as possible in favor of more natural English alternatives. This supports the other claims made about linguistic clarity and its importance. If I can avoid misinterpretations and confusion for my potential readers by adopting an easy and clear language, then this should be one of my main goals in writing.

4) PREPARATION AND GROUNDWORK

If I am writing an essay about a topic of my choice, my main goal is for my arguments to be as persuasive as possible. This requires a lot of time, firstly regarding the one invested in finding sources to support my claims and more importantly, those that challenge them so I can sharpen my argument. Secondly, essay writing needs time that is not spent on the text. As we would say in Germany, good ideas are like good dough, you have to let them rest, so they can rise to their highest potential. Often the best reflections about a certain topic I am working on are not coming while I am actively thinking about it. Once I close the editing software and occupy myself with different things, my brain will subconsciously process my thoughts and connect them with previous knowledge. Because

of this, the most unique insights can sometimes be found when your brain manages to connect two subjects that seem completely separate on paper. For this reason, it is important not to rush essays and allow your ideas time to rise.

Furthermore, it is important to have a broad knowledge base about your topic. After writing down what I already know and organizing the knowledge into headings and bullet points, I like to start with what I would call the research funnel. Reading broadly and intensively about the overall topic to get a good understanding of the discussions surrounding the topic and then becoming more selective and specific in researching. Following this, I should organize all of this research data as well as my arguments, which will support the structured and clear approach outlined in the other points.

5) PLAGIARISM

It is important to provide proper sources for your data and arguments. Firstly, acknowledging the work and research of other researchers is proper academic etiquette. Secondly, readers need to be able to know that you are not inventing results to support your opinions. By making your sources transparent, you allow readers to follow up on your arguments and form their own opinion by reading your references.

There are two types of **citations** used (EUCLID 2019, 6) to do this. The first type, in-text citations, has to be used when directly quoting another person's work or paraphrasing an argument. The second type is the bibliography, which is the list of all works cited. All works mentioned in in-text citations have to be part of the final bibliography. Footnotes should not be mixed with in-text citations. If you want to provide additional information that is helpful for the argument but might disturb the flow of reading, this information can be given via footnote.

Direct **quotations** should only be used when necessary. If used too excessively, your work might read like a collection of other people's arguments and lack a proper personal contribution. To support the structure of your work, there are stylistic rules to follow when directly quoting. Usually, a quote can be included in the text and it suffices to mark it with the appropriate quotation marks. Should the quotation extend over twenty lines of text, it has to be indented to improve readability. One important element that gets mistaken by a lot of even academic writers is the meaning of paraphrasing. It does not mean to just replace some words and otherwise keep the sentence structure identical. Because English is not my native language, I rely a lot on taking notes word by word during the reading process which increases the risk of following original sentences too closely. I will try to integrate this behavioral shift during the process of taking notes to improve.

6) RESEARCH AS A SERVICE

All the points made previously feed into this argument. My research should be a service, not only to me through learning more about the workings of our world, but also a humble one to the scientific community as well as to the overall society. What this means

is a paradigm shift in how I approach my writing, which also stems from several years of working as a communication specialist. All writing is an act of communication. How my writing is read, understood, and potentially cited is in big parts out of my hands because it involves communicative acts of other people. What I can ensure however is to make my research as clear and structured as possible.

This also requires that I check my arguments against other viewpoints and try to challenge myself to see if my theories and arguments hold up. Putting it down as *arguing against myself* (EUCLID 2019, 14) made me understand on a pragmatic level how to approach this which is why this was especially valuable to me. Not representing different viewpoints and opinions is harmful in more than one way. Firstly, I would be distorting the findings of a whole field. Secondly, this would also harm my work and its credibility. If my theories only hold up when not confronted with other viewpoints, then my theories would require more refining. Once readers notice that you are misrepresenting research findings, they might start discrediting your whole work, even if it is based on valuable and empirical data.

7) CONCLUSION

During my previous bachelor's and master's degrees, I have already learned a lot about how to research, structure, and finally write compelling yet scientifically sound papers and was initially curious what this course could add to my past studies. After completing it, I have indeed taken some new insights from this course, mostly about the delicacies of the English language as well as the numerous distinctions between GB and US conventions. Additionally, the material underlined the importance of clarity and structure and updated my existing knowledge from previous studies. Therefore, this period has proven to be a great summary and reminder of rules I have already known as well as a great resource for questions that will surely arise during the process of writing a doctoral thesis in English, a foreign language for me.

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